

BLISTERING OF NEAT RESINS : A NEW MECHANICAL APPROACH.

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ABSTRACT

Fiberglass reinforced polyester laminates are subject to blistering when immersed in sea water. A research programme has been entered at IFREMER BREST Center in order to study this osmotic process in both sea and distilled water, under several conditions of accelerated testing. This paper presents a mechanical model for evaluation of the internal pressure in blisters. That model consists in representing a blister as a circular membrane clamped on its edge and uniformly loaded. First, tests at high temperature and in distilled water are carried out using neat polyester resin samples, on which large circular cavities develop with the osmotic phenomenon. Experimental results allow to determine pressure, radial blistering rates and internal stresses versus time. An equilibrium is reached quickly, pressures vary from 1-2 MPa to 0 MPa, (good agreement with literature values), stresses at the edge exceed the ultimate stress of polyester, confirming the growing of the cavity parallel to the surface exposure. A best knowledge of mechanical properties at high temperature, and chromatographic analysis will confirm results.

KEYWORDS : Composites, polyester resins, sea water, blisters, mechanical model.

1- INTRODUCTION

The IFREMER Brest Centre has been involved for ten years in research programmes concerning the physical, chemical and mechanical behaviour of Fiber Reinforced Plastics in marine environment. These materials, mainly glass fiber reinforced polyester with gelcoat, are sensitive to an osmotic phenomenon leading to a delamination of both coating and laminate. The origin of this phenomenon is due to the action of gelcoat or the resin which behave as a semi-permeable membrane between the solvent (sea or fresh water) and high solutes concentration sites in laminates (figure 1).

The osmotic sites provide from porosity (air bubbles), disc-cracking (due to differential swelling with water absorption), hydrosoluble impurities or

fairly crosslinked areas, where water can condense and hydrolyze polymer chains [1]. An osmotic pressure arises from high concentration of hydrosoluble materials sites (equation (1)), inducing a swelling of the gelcoat (blistering on laminates) and of the neat resin (large circular cavities, parallel to the surface exposure) (figure 2).

The variation versus time of this internal pressure is an interesting parameter to be analyzed in order to predict the stresses in the materials and their life time. Except gas/liquid chromatography analyses that can give access to the pressure at a given time, by the determination of solutes concentrations, few others methods are available in litterature to estimate the pressure versus time. Preliminary accelerated weathering tests have been carried out on commonly used neat polyester resins. A mechanical model is proposed in this paper in order to predict the evolution of pressure inside a blister and stresses in the material versus time. This model consists in assuming a blister, developping on neat resins, to a clamped edge membrane under a uniform load which allows a quick determination of the internal pressure.

Figure 1 : Osmotic process through a semipermeable membrane.

Figure 2: View of an osmotic cavity in neat polyester resin

2- MECHANICAL MODELLING

Some authors estimate the critical pressure required to create a disc crack in polyester resin from thermodynamical calculations :

$$\text{WALTER [2] : } P_c = [3/2 * E * \Gamma / b]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where P_c is the pressure in MPa, E the Young' modulus in MPa, Γ the superficial energy in J/m^2 , b the width in μm . So, for $b=1 \mu m$, $E=3000$ MPa, and $\Gamma=200 J/m^2$ (approximate value for unsaturated polyester) then, $P_c=30$ MPa.

$$\text{SACK [3] : } P_c = [\pi / 2 * E / (1 - \nu^2) * \Gamma / a^2]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

with ν as Poisson's ratio, a a radius of the crack in m. So, with $a=0.01$ m, $\nu=0.3$, $E=3000$ MPa, and $\Gamma=200 J/m^2$ then $P_c= 30$ MPa.

But these estimates remain hasardous because of the difficulty to determinate an accurate superficial energy : this energy can be divided by 5 or 10 when the resin is plastified with water [4].

Furthermore, these last models are not sufficient to determine the pressure

inside macroscopic cavities (like blisters) versus time and the stresses. They can't be applied to blisters that have large radii and deflections in regards of their thickness. Consequently, a blister is best represented by a circular thin membrane with fixed and elastic edge, under a uniform load over entire internal surface (figure 3).

Figure 3 : Blister simulated as a circular clamped membrane under uniform load. w is the deflection, a the radius, p the pressure (intensity of load), t is the thickness.

The interest of such a model is that the maximal deflection at the center w_0 , the radius a and the thickness t are sufficient to determine pressure p , stresses at center and edge and their evolution versus time of weathering.

Timoshenko [4] studied the case of large deflection of plates uniformly loaded with the following hypothesis :

- The plate is isotropic, circular and uniformly loaded so that the strain $w(r)$ is equal for points at a distance r from the center O (case of symmetrical bending). The deflection curve can be studied only along a diametrical section through the axis of symmetry.
- Maximal deflection/thickness ratio is less than 10.
- No plasticity occurs, since unsaturated polyester have a quasi elastic behaviour at room temperature.
- The plate is elastically (non perfectly) clamped on its edge.
- Furthermore, it will be supposed that the internal surface under pressure is not subjected to hydrolysis (case of constant thickness of the plate).

21- SOLUTION FOR SMALL DEFLECTIONS ($w_0 < t$)

The solution for symmetrical bending of laterally loaded circular plates is given by TIMOSHENKO [4] under the following differential equation (4) :

$$\frac{d^3w}{dr^3} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d^2w}{dr^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{dw}{dr} = \frac{Q}{D} \quad (4)$$

r : radius
 $w(r)$: deflection
 Q : shearing force

The flexural rigidity is $D = E/12(1-\nu^2) * t^3$ (5), where E is Young's modulus, t thickness of the plate, and ν Poisson's ratio.

Figure 4 shows the shearing force and deflection $w(r)$.

Figure 4 : Representation of the shearing force Q and the deflection $w(r)$.

The magnitude of the shearing force Q at a distance r from the center of the plate O is determined from equation (6) : $2 \pi r Q = \pi r^2 p$ (6), p pressure uniformly distributed over entire surface.

Substituting in equation (4), and integrating 3 times, the deflection $w(r)$ is equal to :

$$w(r) = pr^4/64D + C1r^2/4 + C2\ln(r/a) + C3 \quad (7)$$

$C1, C2, C3$ are integration constants found from conditions at the center and at the edges of the plate. If the edges are clamped, the slope of the deflection surface at edge must be zero in the radial direction for $r=a$ and for $r=0$. Furthermore, deflection at edge is zero, hence :

$$C2=0, C3=p a^4/64D, C1=-p a^2/8$$

Substituting in equation (7), then :

$$w(r) = p/64D (a^2-r^2)^2, \quad (8) \quad \text{or} \quad w(r) = pa^4/64D (1-r^2/a^2)^2 \quad (9)$$

The maximal deflection w_0 (at center) is $w_0 = pa^4/64D$ (10). So the intensity of load p varies linearly with the maximal deflection. The corresponding elastic energy is given by $W=32/3 \pi D w_0^2/a^2$ (11). The variation of $w(r)/w_0$ versus r/a is represented on figure 5. Maximal stresses are at the edge [4].

Figure 5 : Theoretical deflection along a diametral section.

22-SOLUTION FOR LARGE DEFLECTION (wo>>t)

Membrane stresses acting on the middle plane of the plate have to be taken into account : the strain in the middle plane can't no more be neglected. Supposing that equation (9) still represents the deflection of the surface, henceforth the pressure p varies like polynom of degree 3 in function of wo, maximal deflection at centre :

$$\frac{(wo/t) + A(wo/t)^3}{pa^4/Et^4} = B(p/E)(a/t)^4 \quad (12) \text{ or, under another form :}$$

$$wo = pa^4/64D', D' = D*[1 + A(wo/t)^2] \quad (13)$$

The flexural rigidity D increases with deflection w(o). A and B are constants : B=3/16 (1-v²), A depends on support conditions :

-WAY and WEI-ZANG-CHIEN [5,6] propose for a perfect clamped edge A=0.545.

-OLSON [7] improves the model by writing :

$$w(r)=wo(1-x^2)(1-\alpha x^2) \quad (14),$$

where x=r/a and α represents the support condition. For a perfect clamped edge plate, A=0.472, α=1. For an elastic edge, A<0.4 and α<1. α can be determined from the slope at the edge.

-TIMOSHENKO [4,8] calculates for a perfect clamped edge A=0.488 and for an elastic edge free to move in radial direction A=0.146.

-REISSNER [9] neglects the first degree term in equation (12) for a thin flexible membrane (like blisters on gelcoat) and so :

$$(wo/t)^3 = 0.290 (p/E) (a/t)^4 \quad (15).$$

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the load P=p/E (a/t)⁴ versus (wo/t) for different values of A. Hence, the influence of support conditions appears clearly on the calculation of pressure p.

As blisters on coated laminates and osmotic cavities on resins grow radially at the edge, TIMOSHENKO's elastic value of A (0.146) is taken for modelling, since perfect clamped edge conditions are not reproduced. Furthermore pressure p is determined with the linear theory (equation 10) because, as some plasticity occurs at high temperature, the real value of A is 0 < A < 0.146.

Figure 6 : Evolution of load P versus (wo/t) ratio for the different theories.

Radial and tangential stresses are explicated in table 1. Two types of stresses exist : membrane stresses (or diaphragm stresses), and bending stresses [11].

MEMBRANE STRESS	σ radial	σ tangential
center O $r=0$	$\frac{1}{2} E (w_0/a)^2$	$\frac{1}{2} E (w_0/a)^2$
edge $r=a$	0	$-1/3 E (w_0/a)^2$

BENDING STRESS	σ' radial	σ' tangential
center O $r=0$	$2.86 E (w_0 t)/a^2$	$2.86 E (w_0 t)/a^2$
edge $r=a$	$-4.40 E (w_0 t)/a^2$	$-1.32 E (w_0 t)/a^2$

Table 1 : Approximate values of stresses.

3- MATERIALS

Tested materials are neat polyester resins, commonly used in boat building industry in FRANCE : isophthalic (iso), orthophthalic (ortho) and tetrahydrophthalic (tetra) resins. Curing of styrene /phthalic resins is performed with methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) as initiator and cobalt octoate as accelerator. A post cure treatment is then applied (2 hours at $T=100^\circ\text{C}$) in order to complete the three dimensionnal network.

31 THERMAL CONTROL

The glassy transition temperatures (T_g) and the rate of curing of the resins are determined through differential scanning calorimetry analysis. Results are exposed in table 2.

32 MECHANICAL CONTROL

Three points bending tests (European standard EN 63) and tensile tests (standard NFT 51034) are carried out from crosslinked resins to calculate flexural and tensile modulus (E_f and E_t), just as ultimate strenght of, σ_t (see table 2).

RESIN	$T_g(^\circ\text{C})$	% CURE	$E_f(\text{MPa})$	$\sigma_f(\text{MPa})$	$E_t(\text{MPa})$	$\sigma_t(\text{MPa})$
ISO	105	93	3500	110	3700	70
ORTHO	95	90	3900	90	4000	54
TETRA	95	90	3800	95	3900	60

Table 2 : Physical and mechanical characteristics of neat resins ISO, ORTHO, TETRA.

4- EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Samples of neat resins (100*100*6 mm large) are immersed during 3000 hours (ORTHO and TETRA) and 5000 hours for ISO in distilled water at high

temperature, $T^{\circ}=80^{\circ}\text{C}$, in order to perform accelerated tests of humid weathering. Parameters that are controlled steadily are :

- Gain of mass, due to water absorption,
- Time of disc-cracking,
- Time of swelling, and then the deflection, radius and the shape of swelling curve at a given time.

These last times coincide with a retaking in water absorption, though the rate of absorbed water in polymer had reached a saturation level. Times of disc cracking and swelling are related to times of hydrolysis in the same conditions of testing, which has been confirmed by MORTAIGNE [11] and STEEL [12] (table3).

RESIN	t (hours) hydrolysis	t (hours) disccracking	t (hours) swelling
ISO	600	700	900
ORTHO	84	100	480
TETRA	250	400	1200

table 3 : Comparison between times of degradation.

Hydrolysis times, in the same conditions of weathering, were determined by mechanical testing, showing an irreversible decrease of ultimate strenght (JACQUEMET [13]). Only one circular cavity (assimilated to a blister) is observed on each sample, and have the following medium dimensions:

ISO (5000 h), radius $a=18$ mm, deflection $w_0=0.7$ mm, thickness $t=1$ mm.

TETRA (3000 h) $a=30$ mm, $w_0=3.0$ mm, $t=1.6$ mm.

ORTHO (3000 h) $a=25$ mm, $w_0=2.4$ mm, $t=1.4$ mm.

41- DEFLECTION CURVES AFTER 3000 h / 5000 h OF AGEING

Deflection $w(r)$ is measured on blisters along a diameter through the axis of symmetry at the center of the plate. Deflection ratios $w(r)/w_0$ versus (r/a) are reported on figure 7 for the different resins.

Figure 7 : Deflection ratio $w(r)/w_0$ versus (r/a) for iso, ortho and tetra resin blisters. Comparison with theoretical curve.

There is a good agreement between experimental deflection curves and theoretical curve in regards of the incertitude : $dr/r=5\%$, $dw(r)/w(r)=6\%$. The mechanical model suits well with the theory of deflection of plate clamped on its edge and uniformly loaded.

42- BLISTERING RATE

After $t=3000$ h for ortho and tetra resins and $t=5000$ h for iso resin, the medium radius observed on blisters is called a^∞ . Figure 8 represents the evolution of the radius ratio $x=(a(t)/a^\infty)$ with time t in hours. A quick evolution is observed from time of swelling, then the radius ratio tends towards 1 as if an equilibrium is reached at long times of ageing. A linear relationship have been found (by linear regression) between $\ln(x)$ and t :

$$\ln(1-x) = -k(t-t_0) \quad \text{or} \quad x(t) = 1 - \exp[-k(t-t_0)] \quad (16)$$

$$x(t) = a(t)/a^\infty,$$

t_0 : time of swelling for a given resin (table 3) (in hours).

k : constant depending on the nature of the resin (in hours⁻¹).

Radial rate can be deduced by deriving (16):

$$dx/dt = k \exp[-k(t-t_0)] \quad (17), \text{ so for } t=t_0, dx(0)/dt=k.$$

Values of k and rates are reported in table 4:

RESIN	K (h ⁻¹)	rate μm/h	correlation fact. r ²
ISO	9.6 E-4 ±0.5E-4	17	0.94
TETRA	31 E-4 ±2E-4	93	0.98
ORTHO	51 E-4 ±4E-4	120	1.01

Table 4 : Values of k and rates of blistering for polyester resins at $T=80^\circ\text{C}$ in distilled water.

Figure 8 : Evolution of radius ratio $(a(t)/a^\infty)$ versus time t in hours.

k seems to vary with the nature of the resin : k increases from iso resin to tetra and ortho, like the YOUNG's modulus and ultimate strenght for these last resins (table 2). Disc crack velocity for a polyester resin can

be found in litterature (AHSBEE [14]), rate are about from 1 to 10 μm/h, but no information concerning the nature of the resin is given.

43- EVOLUTION OF PRESSURE VERSUS TIME

Pressure of swelling is calculated from equations (10) and (12). The evolution of *p* (in MPa) versus time *t* (hours) is shown on figures 9,10,11. Incertitude on results is calculated from equation (11) :

$$dp/p = dwo/wo + 4*da/a = 1 + 4.5 = 5-6\%$$

Good relationship by power regression is obtained for *p(t)* versus time *t*, for *t>=to* : $p(t) = po [t-to]^b$ (18), where *po* and *b* are constants, given in table 5.

The shape of *p(t)* curves shows that pressure tends quickly to zero with time of weathering : cracks in the thickness of the plate increase the rate of exchange between the solvent (distilled water) and the solutes, hence an equilibrium of pressure is reached.

RESIN	constant b	correlation factor
ISO	-2.55±0.15	r ² =0.94
	-2.34±0.12	r ² =0.94
TETRA	-1.63±0.11	r ² =0.98
	-1.52±0.12	r ² =0.97
ORTHO	-1.43±0.09	r ² =0.97
	-1.49±0.08	r ² =0.96

Table 5 : Values of constants *b* for polyester resins, $p(t)=po[t-to]^b$.

Figure 9 : Pressure *p(t)* in MPa versus time *t* in hours, ISO resin.

Figure 10 : Pressure *p(t)* in MPa versus time *t* in hours, TETRA resin.

Figure 11 : Pressure $p(t)$ in MPa versus time t in hours, ORTHO resin.

The pressure determined by mechanical modelling is in good agreement with estimated values found in literature by others methods (quantitative chromatographic analyses) [1],[15],[16],[17].

44) EVOLUTION OF STRESSES VERSUS TIME

Stresses are calculated from approximate solutions (table 1) and are represented versus time of ageing on figures 12,13, and 14.

Figure 12 : Stresses versus time, ISO resin.

Figure 13 : Stresses versus time, TETRA resin.

Figure 14 : Stresses versus time, ORTHO resin.

These figures show that the stresses are higher at the edge of blisters than at the center. Furthermore, edge stresses (mainly bending stresses) reach an upper limit which is the ultimate limit of the polyester (from 80 to 120 MPa), explaining why the circular cavity grows parallel to the exposure surface.

5- CONCLUSION

Accelerated tests of humid ageing, carried out on neat polyester resins allow to model circular blisters that develop parallel to the surface exposure. Internal pressure can be evaluated with that mechanical model (it varies from 1-2 MPa to 0), radial propagation velocities of blisters are determined, and results show that the osmotic process stops quickly, due to an equilibrium of solutes concentrations. This equilibrium is reached faster because cracks appear in the thickness of the plate. The pressures are in good agreement with those found in literature just as radial rates of blistering. A best knowledge of resins mechanical characteristics at high temperature will improve results. In more, these last ones have to be confirmed by chromatographic analysis calculations.

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